

Solving fractional pantograph optimal control problems using Fibonacci wavelets

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ABSTRACT. In this study, we present a computational method for solving fractional pantograph optimal control problems. To solve this class of optimal control problems, we used the Fibonacci wavelet and Ritz method. Here, we propose an extra Caputo pseudo-operational matrix and pantograph operational matrix for the Fibonacci wavelets. Combining the matrices and the Ritz and collocation methods, the considered problem is converted to a system of algebraic equations. The applicability of the scheme is demonstrated by an illustrative example.

Keywords: Fibonacci wavelet, Ritz method, pantograph optimal control problem

1. Introduction

In this study, we focus on the following problem.

$$(1) \quad \min \mathfrak{J}(x, u) = \frac{1}{2}x^T(1)Qx(1) + \frac{1}{2} \int_0^1 \left(x^T(t)R_1(t)x(t) + u^T(t)R_2(t)u(t) \right) dt,$$

subject to

$$(2) \quad D^\alpha x(t) = A(t)x(t) + B(t)x(\tau t) + C(t)u(t) + E(t)u(\tau t), \quad N-1 < \alpha \leq N, \quad \tau \in (0, 1),$$

where $x^{(i)}(0) = \rho_i$, $i = 0, 1, \dots, N-1$, and R_1, R_2 are, respectively, semi-positive and positive-definite appropriate matrices in which each entry of these matrices is a continuous function of available t . Q is a semi-positive definite appropriate matrix. We assume that $A(t), B(t), C(t)$ and $E(t)$ are known matrix functions with appropriate dimensions. In the problems, D^α denotes the Caputo fractional derivative [4]. The pantograph optimal control problem is a kind of delay problem that few investigations are devoted to solving this problem. The composite Legendre method was applied to solve the optimal control of linear pantograph-type system [1]. In this manuscript, Fibonacci wavelets are defined. Then, we present a new numerical method based on these functions and Ritz and collocation methods to solve fractional pantograph optimal control problems. To do this, an extra Caputo pseudo-operational matrix and pantograph operational matrix are proposed for the mentioned wavelets.

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2. Fibonacci wavelets and properties

Fibonacci wavelets are presented as follows [3]

$$(3) \quad \psi_{n,m}(t) = \begin{cases} 2^{\frac{k-1}{2}} \widehat{F}_m(2^{k-1}t - n + 1), & \frac{n-1}{2^{k-1}} \leq t < \frac{n}{2^{k-1}}, \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

with $\widehat{F}_m(t) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\int_0^1 \widetilde{F}_m^2(t) dt}} \widetilde{F}_m(t)$, $\widetilde{F}_m(t) = \sum_{i=0}^{\lfloor \frac{m}{2} \rfloor} \binom{m-i}{i} t^{m-2i}$, $n \geq 0$, where $\widetilde{F}_m(t)$ is Fibonacci polynomials, m is the order for these polynomials, $n = 1, 2, \dots, 2^{k-1}$ and k is a positive integer.

2.1. Ritz method and function approximation. Here, we approximate an arbitrary function $g(t)$ using Fibonacci wavelets as

$$g(t) \approx \sum_{\hat{m}=1}^{\hat{M}} \theta(t) g_{\hat{m}} \psi_{\hat{m}}(t) + \zeta(t) = \theta(t) G^T \Psi(t) + \zeta(t),$$

subject to

$$\Psi(t) = [\psi_{1,1}(t), \dots, \psi_{1,M}(t), \dots, \psi_{2^{k-1},1}(t), \dots, \psi_{2^{k-1},M}(t)]^T = [\psi_1(t), \psi_2(t), \dots, \psi_{\hat{M}}(t)]^T,$$

$$G = [g_{1,1}(t), \dots, g_{1,M}(t), \dots, g_{2^{k-1},1}(t), \dots, g_{2^{k-1},M}(t)]^T = [g_1(t), g_2(t), \dots, g_{\hat{M}}(t)]^T,$$

where $\hat{M} = 2^{k-1}M$. Note that $\zeta(t)$ satisfies to the initial conditions in Eq. (2), $\theta(t)$ satisfies to the homogenous initial conditions and these functions are not unique. We consider

$$\theta(t) = t^N, \quad \zeta(t) = \rho_0 + \rho_1 t + \dots + \rho_{N-1} \frac{t^{N-1}}{(N-1)!}.$$

2.2. Extra Caputo pseudo-operational matrix. Due to the above consideration, we seek to find an extra Caputo pseudo-operational matrix for Fibonacci wavelets in the following form.

$$(4) \quad D^\alpha (t^N \Psi(t)) = \mathfrak{C}(t, \alpha) \Psi(t),$$

where, $\mathfrak{C}(t, \alpha)$ is the mentioned matrix. On the other hand, we can expand $\Psi(t)$ into the piecewise Taylor functions ($\Phi(t)$), given in [2], as $\Psi(t) = \Lambda \Phi(t)$, where $\Lambda = [\lambda_{r,s}]$, Λ is the transformation matrix of Fibonacci wavelets to the piecewise Taylor functions

$$\varphi_{i,j}(t) = \sum_{r=1}^{2^{k-1}} \sum_{s=1}^M \lambda_{r,s} \psi_{r,s}(t),$$

$$\text{in which } \varphi_{i,j}(t) = \begin{cases} t^j, & t \in [\frac{i-1}{2^{k-1}}, \frac{i}{2^{k-1}}), \\ 0, & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases} \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, 2^{k-1}, \quad j = 0, 1, \dots, M-1,$$

$$\Phi(t) = [\varphi_{1,0}(t), \dots, \varphi_{1,M-1}(t), \dots, \varphi_{2^{k-1},0}(t), \dots, \varphi_{2^{k-1},M-1}(t)]^T = [\varphi_1(t), \varphi_2(t), \dots, \varphi_{\hat{M}}(t)]^T.$$

Besides, the extra Caputo pseudo-operational matrix for the piecewise Taylor functions is as

follows [2] $D^\alpha (t^N \Phi(t)) = \mathfrak{N}(t, \alpha) \Phi(t)$, in which $\mathfrak{N}(t, \alpha) = \text{diag} \left[\underbrace{\mathfrak{n}(t, \alpha), \mathfrak{n}(t, \alpha), \dots, \mathfrak{n}(t, \alpha)}_{2^{k-1}} \right]$, and

$$\mathfrak{n}(t, \alpha) = t^{N-\alpha} \text{diag} \left[\frac{\Gamma(N+1)}{\Gamma(N+1-\alpha)}, \dots, \frac{\Gamma(N+M)}{\Gamma(N+M-\alpha)} t^{M-1} \right].$$

Finally, utilizing the previous discussion, we can derive the mentioned matrix for Fibonacci wavelets in the following procedure:

$$(5) \quad D^\alpha (t^N \Psi(t)) = D^\alpha (t^N \Lambda \Phi(t)) = \Lambda D^\alpha (t^N \Phi(t))$$

$$= \Lambda \mathfrak{N}(t, \alpha) \Phi(t) = \Lambda \mathfrak{N}(t, \alpha) \Lambda^{-1} \Psi(t) = \mathfrak{C}(t, \alpha) \Psi(t),$$

where $\mathfrak{C}(t, \alpha) = \Lambda \mathfrak{N}(t, \alpha) \Lambda^{-1}$ is the mentioned extra Caputo pseudo-operational matrix.

2.3. Pantograph operational matrix. Let $\Psi(\tau t) = \mathfrak{V}(\tau) \Psi(t)$, where $\mathfrak{V}(\tau)$ is the pantograph operational matrix for Fibonacci wavelets. Moreover, we know this operational matrix for the piecewise Taylor functions is as follows [2]

$$\Phi(\tau t) = \hat{\Theta} \Phi(t), \quad \hat{\Theta} = \text{diag} \left[\underbrace{\Theta, \Theta, \dots, \Theta}_{2^{k-1}} \right],$$

where $\Theta = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & \tau & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & \tau^{M-1} \end{pmatrix}$. Then, similar to the previous subsection, we can write

$$\Psi(\tau t) = \Lambda \Phi(\tau t) = \Lambda \hat{\Theta} \Phi(t) = \Lambda \hat{\Theta} \Lambda^{-1} \Psi(t) = \mathfrak{V}(\tau) \Psi(t),$$

where $\mathfrak{V}(\tau) = \Lambda \hat{\Theta} \Lambda^{-1}$ is the pantograph operational matrix for the mentioned wavelets.

3. Numerical method

In this section, we propose a numerical method for solving the considered problem Eqs. (1)-(2), then, we approximate the unknown functions as

$$(6) \quad x(t) \approx X^T t^N \Psi(t) + \zeta(t), \quad u(t) \approx U^T \Psi(t),$$

where $\zeta(t) = \rho_0 + \rho_1 t + \dots + \rho_{N-1} \frac{t^{N-1}}{(N-1)!}$. Then, using the extra Caputo pseudo-operational matrix and the pantograph operational matrix, we have

$$D^\alpha(x(t)) \approx X^T \mathfrak{C}(t, \alpha) \Psi(t) + \hat{\zeta}(t), \quad \hat{\zeta}(t) = D^\alpha(\zeta(t)),$$

and $x(\tau t) \approx X^T \tau^N \mathfrak{V}(\tau) t^N \Psi(t) + \zeta(\tau t)$, $u(\tau t) \approx U^T \mathfrak{V}(\tau) \Psi(t) + \zeta(\tau t)$. We insert the approximations in the functional $\mathfrak{J}$, and the system dynamics equation (named $\tilde{\mathfrak{A}}$), then, by applying the collocation method for this equation at the Newton-Cotes points, we derive a system of algebraic equations (named $\tilde{\mathfrak{A}}(t_\xi)$), where $\tilde{\mathfrak{A}}(t_\xi) = 0$. To solve the optimization problem given in Eq. (1), due to the above discussion, we have

$$\mathfrak{J}^* = \mathfrak{J} + v_\xi \tilde{\mathfrak{A}}, \quad \xi = 1, 2, \dots, \hat{M},$$

in which v_ξ are the unknown multiplier's coefficients. The necessary conditions for minimizing $\mathfrak{J}^*$ is that the following relations hold.

$$(7) \quad \frac{\partial \mathfrak{J}^*}{\partial X} = 0, \quad \frac{\partial \mathfrak{J}^*}{\partial U} = 0, \quad \frac{\partial \mathfrak{J}^*}{\partial \Upsilon} = 0, \quad \Upsilon = [v_\xi], \quad \xi = 1, 2, \dots, \hat{M}.$$

The above equations are solved using "FindRoot" package, and the unknown vector X, U and Υ are determined.

4. Numerical example

EXAMPLE 4.1. Consider the following F-POCP

$$\mathfrak{J} = \frac{1}{2} \int_0^1 \left(x^2(t) - 2e^{-t}x(t) + u^2(t) + e^{-\frac{3}{4}t}u(t) \right) dt,$$

$$D^\alpha x(t) = \frac{1}{2}x\left(\frac{3}{4}t\right) - x(t) + u(t), \quad 0 < \alpha \leq 1, \quad x(0) = 1.$$

The optimal values are $x(t) = e^{-t}$, $u(t) = -\frac{1}{2}e^{-\frac{3}{4}t}$, and $\mathfrak{J} = -0.28090533251188110079$, when $\alpha = 1$. We solve this problem by implementing the proposed method for various choices of k and M . Table 1 presents the numerical results for $\alpha = 1$. Here, we report the numerical value of $\mathfrak{J}$,

then these values are compared with composite Legendre method [1]. The plot of absolute errors for $x(t)$ and $u(t)$ in $k = 2, M = 5$ are shown in Figure 1. Besides, the graphs of numerical solutions of $x(t)$, and $u(t)$ for $k = 2, M = 3$ and different choices of β are displayed in Figure 2.

TABLE 1. Comparison of the numerical value of $\mathfrak{J}$.

Method	$\mathfrak{J}$
Composite Legendre method ($N = K = 1, M = 5$)	-0.2809053325117
Composite Legendre method ($N = K = 1, M = 6$)	-0.28090533251181091
Present method ($k = 1, M = 5$)	-0.28090533251105
Present method ($k = 2, M = 5$)	-0.28090533251166
Present method ($k = 3, M = 5$)	-0.28090533251181

FIGURE 1. The graphs of absolute errors of $x(t)$ (right) and $u(t)$ (left) for $k = 2, M = 5$ and different choices of α .

FIGURE 2. The graphs of approximate solutions of $x(t)$ (right) and $u(t)$ (left) for different values of α , and $k = 2, M = 3$.

5. Conclusion

Here, we proposed a numerical scheme to solve a class of delay fractional optimal control problems. To this aim, we used the Fibonacci wavelets and the collocation and Ritz methods. The applicability of the scheme is demonstrated by an illustrative example, moreover, a comparison with the composite Legendre method shows the preference of this scheme.

References

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